

ON THE CONFIGURATION OF VAK LEARNING STYLES: A CASE STUDY ON VOCABULARY TEACHING IN ARMENIA

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Abstract

The following research studies the implementation of the Visual-Auditory-Kinesthetic (VAK) model of learning in vocabulary instruction for Armenian high school students. In response to the growing concerns of effective personalized learning, this study seeks to find out whether completing vocabulary tasks based on the students' sensory preferences would improve language acquisition, motivation, and performance. The sample consisted of 18 tenth graders, half of whom served as a control group and were taught using traditional methods, and an experimental group whose instruction utilized VAK-based activities. Assessing vocabulary knowledge and learner engagement was done through pre-test and post-test questionnaires. Results reveal that students in the experimental group outperformed their peers enrolled in the control group. Enhanced vocabulary recall, contextual use, and increased participation in class were indeed noted. All three learner categories, visual, auditory, and kinesthetic, profited from their respective tasks, while those with mixed preferences displayed the greatest gains. The findings indicated that the VAK model encourages students' initiative and enables active choice in their learning, resulting in increased retention of more vocabulary for longer periods. Evidence from this study calls for the adoption of multimodal instructional approaches to ESL/EFL instruction responsive to the varying cognitive and emotional needs of learners.

Keywords: VAK styles, personalized learning, sensory preferences, vocabulary, motivational factors, student motivation, visual learners, auditory learners, kinesthetic learners, pre-test, post-test, control group, experimental group, learner engagement, etc...

Introduction

Today's dynamic educational landscape requires specific attention to the diverse needs of learners. Teachers have a wide variety of teaching methods at their disposal, namely in the field of teaching languages. That's why educational psychology suggests that students have particular learning styles and should be considered when tailoring tasks according to students' needs. Throughout their developmental stages, students are likely to excel with the help of various learning styles. The VAK model offers tailored strategies that align with individual learning preferences. By integrating visual aids, auditory input, and kinesthetic activities, educators can create more effective and memorable learning experiences. In the following article, the VAK learning styles model will be utilized, specifically in vocabulary instruction, to help students boost their knowledge with the help of their preferred learning styles.

Research methods: quantitative experimental method, pre-test and post-test design, control and experimental grouping, questionnaire method, descriptive statistical analysis, observation method, comparative analysis, content analysis, case study. **Statement of the problem** The Main research theme lies in the modern educational context, where the increasing emphasis on personalized learning and inclusive pedagogy necessitates innovative strategies to cater to diverse learner needs. The VAK learning model is recognized for its applicability in differentiated instruction, making it particularly relevant in vocabulary acquisition, a cornerstone of effective language learning. Therefore, by

addressing learners' preferred styles in learning and applying the VAK styles in vocabulary instruction helps students and teachers reach academic success.

The aim of the research The research aims to explore and evaluate the efficiency of the VAK learning model in vocabulary instruction and its effect on motivation boost.

Research questions The following article aims to investigate over the following questions;

1. Whether the VAK learning styles model meets the needs of students' sensory preferences in learning while improving their motivation and engagement?
2. How can VAK learning styles be applied among high school students to help them in their vocabulary acquisition?

Theoretical background

Language learning and teaching in the 21st century is clearly defined by its efficiency. Trends that are now becoming mainstream, such as the orientation and individual learning tracks, which involve the mastery of the language in an industry-specific context, have emerged. A learning style is a behavior the learner demonstrates in terms of social, cognitive, physiological, and affective engagement that delineates how an individual manages to interact with the teaching and learning environment. (Mac Keracher D., 2004, p. 71). Another definition provided by one well-known scholar, Reid (2002), defines a learning style as a way a learner habitually absorbs, organizes, and processes new information when mastering new skills, which makes it a method that adds value. This helps the

learner remember much more easily after these activities, enabling the processes of new skills to be set into place. For long-term memory and retention to occur, each student's particular method of processing information needs to be understood by identifying what would best capture their attention and how to further it. In revealing these unique traits and styles, there is a need to employ a multi-faceted model of learning that captures the learner's interests and strengths. Elements such as age and maturation have physiological components. Education sociology is equally important and factors of a lower class Sirin, S. R. (2005), through a meta analyze review show that lower socioeconomic status has less access to resources, better learning environments, and educational opportunities, affect grades and academic achievement. Psychological elements assist with the cognitive learning process. For example, some learners tend to be more visual, auditory, or kinesthetic than others (D. A. Kolb, 1984). In Posner M.L., Petersen S.E. (1990) attention system of the human brain. Emotional elements are participators in the learning process, but never passive, positive emotions make it easier for learners to be focused on their learning tasks. VAK theory has become particularly popular in the accelerated learning community due to its benefits in its early applications. The rationale is simple. The Visual-Auditory-Kinesthetic learning strategy does not incorporate H. Gardner's multiple intelligences or D. Kolb's theory; instead, the VAK model offers a different lens for comprehending and clarifying an individual's thinking, learning preferences and dominant skill sets. Theories and models offer a variety of classifications of learning styles, often paying attention to different angles of the problem on how learners learn. Numerous classifications of learning styles are based on the "type" theories and categorizes learners in groups as presumed separate categories as opposed to giving ranks on varying degrees on different aspects. This can be traced to the groundbreaking typological theorizing in personality spearheaded by psychiatrist and psychoanalyst C. G. Jung (1964). Jung's ideas have been put together with the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) test - a psychometric tool created in the US that became popular after the 1960s and is still widely used today. The MBTI assigns people into groups with the supposed purpose of assisting them with career choices. However, there is little evidence to show that people can be accurately mapped onto groups as this test proposes (e.g., J.N. Druckman and L.W. Porter, 1991). Regardless of this lack of empirical support, the MBTI's persistent popularity suggests people's willingness to always want to know their "type" and "personality," which has then led to the creation of other assessments, such as learning-style ones that are designed using typological schemes. A connected reason for the spread of the learning-styles approach is responsibility. For instance, when either an adult or a child does not perform well at school, it is often easier to assume that the problem lies within the schooling system than in one's efforts. In other words, instead of accepting personal failures, it might be easier to say that there was not enough effort to adjust the teaching methods and material to the students' needs. The VAK styles seem to suit the rest of the approaches to instruction because such learners

are considered active participants with specific needs and interests. It is further explained how the learning is made personal in these schools as it relates to the specific interests and experiences of the students. Customization of curriculum and activities is done considering each student's strengths, weaknesses, and interests. The outcome is a learning system that is flexible and individualistic instead of a rigid system where everyone is treated the same (S.L. Bates, 2014). In other words, personalized learning aims to make sure every student succeeds through direct responses to their varying needs. One reason is that personalized learning designs the participation of students beyond that of a 'consumer' of knowledge to that of a 'co-producer and collaborator' of their preferred style of education. Also, as noted by T. Bentley and K. Miller (2004), personalization is a strategy in learning that focuses more on the child learner, leading to better learning outcomes and experiences. It also increases the school's credibility for appreciating and supporting students' personalized learning. The VAK style identifies three types of learners according to their preferred learning style.

Visual learners constitute a significant proportion of the population, displaying distinct preferences and strategies for acquiring and processing information (R. Dunn and K. Dunn, 1985). This article delves into the characteristics, learning styles, advantages, challenges, and instructional implications associated with visual learners. Drawing upon empirical research and theoretical frameworks, it offers insights into optimizing educational practices to cater to the diverse needs of visual learners in various educational settings. In the realm of education, understanding the diverse learning styles of students is paramount for effective instruction. Visual learners, characterized by their preference for visual stimuli, encompass a substantial portion of the student population. Visual learners exhibit distinctive traits that shape their learning experiences. They possess a keen inclination towards visual stimuli, such as graphs, charts, diagrams, and images, which facilitate comprehension and retention. According to Fleming's VAK model (N.D. Fleming and C. Mills, 1992), visual learners demonstrate a propensity for spatial understanding and prefer visual representations of information. They often display strong observational skills, thriving in environments that emphasize visual aids and demonstrations. Visual learning offers several advantages that enhance comprehension, retention, and engagement among students. Research suggests that visual stimuli can expedite information processing and facilitate deeper understanding (R.E. Mayer, 2009). By harnessing the power of imagery and spatial representation, visual learners can grasp complex concepts with greater ease. The way that visual aids promote active learning is by stimulating curiosity and encouraging exploration (T.N. Höffler and D. Leutner, 2007). This proactive engagement enhances student motivation and fosters a deeper connection with the subject matter. Despite its benefits, visual learning presents certain challenges that warrant attention. In environments where visual aids are scarce or inadequately utilized, visual learners may struggle to engage with the material effectively. Additionally, reliance solely on visual modalities may pose

difficulties for accommodating diverse learning preferences within a heterogeneous classroom (R. E. Clark, 2012). Excessive reliance on passive visual consumption, such as prolonged screen time, can lead to cognitive overload and diminish learning outcomes (J. Sweller, 1994). Understanding the characteristics, learning styles, advantages, challenges, and instructional implications associated with visual learning is essential for promoting inclusive and effective educational practices. By adopting a holistic approach that embraces the diverse needs of visual learners, educators can create enriching learning experiences that foster student engagement, comprehension, and success. **Auditory** learners represent a distinct group whose preferences and needs warrant attention in educational practice. Auditory learners process information primarily through listening, preferring auditory input over visual or kinesthetic stimuli. Despite comprising a substantial portion of the student population, auditory learners often encounter challenges in traditional educational settings that prioritize visual and textual modes of instruction. Therefore, understanding the unique characteristics and learning strategies of auditory learners is essential for educators to design inclusive and effective teaching practices. Auditory learners exhibit distinct characteristics that distinguish them from other learning styles. They demonstrate a heightened sensitivity to sounds, an inclination towards verbal communication, and a preference for auditory stimuli Coffield, F., Moseley, D., Hugo, V., & Elliott, J. (2004). These learners often excel in activities such as listening to lectures, participating in discussions, and engaging in oral presentations. This type of learner tends to have strong auditory memory, enabling them to retain information conveyed through spoken language more effectively than visual or tactile modalities. They learn best through hearing lectures, discussions, and audio recordings. They may actively use word association, video watching, group discussions, taping notes etc. A group of prominent scientists, such as Pashler, H., McDaniel, M., Rohrer, D., & Bjork, R. (2009) are of the opinion that for optimizing learning outcomes for auditory learners, educators can employ various strategies tailored to their preferences and strengths. Incorporating auditory elements into instruction, such as verbal explanations, recorded lectures, and audio materials, can enhance comprehension and retention for auditory learners. Encouraging active listening and providing opportunities for verbal interaction and discussion can facilitate deeper engagement and knowledge acquisition. Leveraging mnemonic devices and rhythmical patterns will also help auditory learners to encode and recall information more efficiently. They extrapolate that recognizing the prevalence of auditory learners in the classroom has significant implications for educational practice. By acknowledging and accommodating diverse learning styles, educators can create inclusive learning environments that cater to the needs of all students, including auditory learners. Implementing multimodal instructional approaches that integrate auditory, visual, and kinesthetic elements can cater to the diverse needs of learners and promote equitable access to education. So, by understanding the distinctive char-

acteristics and preferences of auditory learners, educators can adopt strategies that optimize their learning experiences and academic outcomes. Embracing inclusivity and diversity in teaching practices not only benefits auditory learners but also enriches the educational experience for all students. **Kinesthetic** learners exhibit distinct characteristics that differentiate them from other learning styles. They are often described as "doers" who prefer to learn through active participation rather than passive observation. According to R. Dunn and K. Dunn (1993), kinesthetic learners have a strong need for physical movement and may become restless or disengaged in traditional lecture-based classrooms. Their learning is enhanced when they can touch, manipulate, or explore materials in a hands-on manner (H. Gardner, 1993). To refine learning outcomes for kinesthetic learners, educators should employ a variety of strategies that align with their preferences. Incorporating movement-based activities, such as role playing, simulations, and experiments, allows kinesthetic learners to engage with content in a meaningful way (N.D. Fleming, 2001). Providing opportunities for kinesthetic learners to physically interact with learning materials, such as through building models or conducting experiments, can deepen their understanding and retention of concepts (R. Felder and L. Silverman, 1988). Despite the benefits of accommodating kinesthetic learners, educators may encounter challenges in meeting their needs within traditional classroom settings. Limited resources, time constraints, and standardized curricula often pose barriers to implementing hands on activities and kinesthetic learning experiences (S. A. Griggs, 1994). Assessing the learning outcomes of kinesthetic learners through traditional methods such as written exams may not accurately capture their understanding and proficiency (C. C. Bonwell and J.A. Eison, 1991). Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to adapt instructional practices and assessment strategies to better align with the needs of kinesthetic learners. To do so, educators play a pivotal role in creating inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of all students, including kinesthetic learners. By incorporating kinesthetic learning activities, providing opportunities for physical movement, and offering alternative assessment methods, educators can better support the academic success and engagement of kinesthetic learners (L. C. Sarasin, 1999). R. Dunn and K. Dunn (1978) suggested that 20-30% of school children appear to be auditory learners, 40% visual learners, and 30-40% kinesthetic or visual/kinesthetic learners. W.B. Barbe and M.N. J. Milone (1981) asserted that in school children, the most prevalent modality strengths are visual (30%) or mixed (30%), followed by auditory (25%), and finally by kinesthetic (15%). G.E. Price, R. Dunn (1980) deduced that the youngest children are most kinesthetic, that there is a development of visual strengths throughout the elementary school years, and that most children are not capable of learning and remembering information by hearing until fifth or sixth grade. M. Carbo (1983) in his writing on readers' style discovered that skilled readers prefer to be instructed through utilizing the visual and auditory senses more than less-skilled readers, who prefer haptic and kinetic learning. It then takes us to the implication that the model of

VAK components differs depending on issues previously discussed. In order to extrapolate, learning styles refer to individual preferences and methods that learners use when engaging with and taking in new information. From the various models of how to determine learning styles, VAK (Visual, Auditory, Kinesthetic) is a very inclusive and convenient model. The VAK model categorizes learners as visual, auditory, and kinesthetic based on their preferred way of learning. The VAK style offers several advantages that make it a valuable tool for educators and learners alike. Firstly, it recognizes the diversity of learners and acknowledges that individuals may have different strengths and preferences when it comes to acquiring knowledge. By addressing visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities, the VAK model provides a holistic framework for designing instruction and learning experiences that cater to a broad range of learning styles. Moreover, the VAK model encourages active engagement and experiential learning, which have been shown to enhance understanding and retention of concepts. Visual learners benefit from diagrams, charts, and images, auditory learners excel with lectures, discussions, and audio recordings, while kinesthetic learners thrive through hands-on activities, movement, and tactile experiences. By incorporating elements from each modality, educators can create dynamic and interactive learning environments that accommodate diverse learning preferences. By embracing the VAK model, educators can effectively personalize instruction by providing multiple avenues for learning and allowing learners to select the modalities that best suit their learning preferences. In essence, the VAK style offers a robust framework for understanding and accommodating diverse learning styles, to teach different aspects of language. Vocabulary, akin to grammar, constitutes an essential component of language acquisition and understanding. A. Herrell and M. Jordan (2004:149), a solid grasp of vocabulary is fundamental in the process of learning a language. The importance of vocabulary in learning a second language (L2) is aptly summarized by D.A. Wilkins, who, as

cited in N. Schmitt, stated, "without grammar, very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary, nothing can be conveyed. (2010, p. 58)" M. Flohr (2008) emphasized that vocabulary is a crucial component of any language course, noting that it must be taught in context to convey meaning effectively and be understood in a foreign language. Therefore, while choosing an aspect for our case study, the preference was immediately given to the vocabulary instruction.

Case Study

Participants The case study was conducted at Shirak State University High School among 18 students (14 girls and 4 boys) studying in grade 10 in the Humanities stream. The average age range was from 15 to 16. To experiment properly, the classroom was later divided into two equal groups of 9 students each. Group 10 A was the control group (CG) taught with usual textbook tasks, and Group 10 B was the experimental group (EG) taught via customized VAK-style tasks. **Instrumentation** Firstly, a questionnaire was given to all 18 students to evaluate students' confidence in their vocabulary, which included questions on what difficulties students face when they study new words in English. The next instrument was a pre-test to check students' knowledge of the topic of family and personality-related words. Later on, after experimenting with both of the groups, a post-test was given consisting of 10 questions around the same words to correctly evaluate the outcomes of VAK-based activities. **Materials** The experiment on the traditional method with a Control group was conducted using S. Bagdassarian and S. Gurdjayant's textbook, published by Manmar Publishing House in 2010, from Unit 8: Who are you? on page 101. For the EG, a variation of the task Word Salad was used, taken from English Teaching Forum Vol. 58, N3, 2020, pp. 46-48. **Procedure** The whole experimental study consists of 4 main stages. Before turning to the stages, the questionnaire developed according to Harvard University's "Developing questionnaires for educational research paper" standards was given to all students. The questionnaire is represented below.

Table 1.

Vocabulary Questionnaire

VOCABULARY QUESTIONNAIRE	YES A LOT	QUITE A BIT	NOT AT ALL	ABSOLUTELY
1. Do you find it difficult to remember new English words after learning them?				
2. Do you have trouble understanding the meaning of new English words in different contexts?				
3. Do you often forget the meaning of English words you have learned?				
4. Do you find it challenging to use new English phrases in conversations?				
5. Do you feel that learning new English words takes too much time and effort?				

To motivate students for the upcoming topic, a series of questions was posed, inviting them to reflect on themselves and their unique personalities. These questions served as a gentle warm-up, seamlessly guiding them toward the next set of tasks, fostering curiosity

and readiness for deeper engagement. Students were asked such questions as:

- Do you think you know yourself?
- How will your best friend describe you?
- Are you tolerant? dominant? attentive? outgoing?

In Stage 1 a pre-test was given to all twelve students on the target topic to check their general knowledge related to family members, personality adjectives. The pre-test is the same for both the control and the experimental group. This was aimed at revealing the general competence of the classroom about this topic, as well as finding the gap in their knowledge in order to provide a room for further improvement. Firstly, a worksheet was given to each student. The pre-test was in the form of a text, from which students were supposed to find 20 family members, relatives, or personality-related words and underline them. Each correct answer had the value of 0.5 points. Students were given 5-10 minutes for the task. After that, the worksheets were collected to draw a general conclusion on students' knowledge of the words. In Stage 2, an experiment was held with the CG to check their comprehension of words related to family members and personality adjectives, as well as the effect and the efficiency of the traditional method. The CG consisted of 6 girls and 3 boys, who had to work on the tasks individually. For this purpose, several tasks were chosen from the textbook. On page 189 in the book there was given a specific vocabulary around which the tasks were developed. Overall, the three tasks together had the value of 10 points. The content of the 3A task is as follows: Students were given 5 statements, for example A man who has good manners is ill-mannered. It's wrong. An ill-mannered man has bad manners. Similarly, students were expected to write the same for the following sentences, 0.5 points for each correct answer.

1. A man who is not sure of himself is self-confident.
2. A man who is always polite is tactless.
3. A man who thinks only of himself is selfish.
4. A man who likes to live in a city is a suburban man.
5. A man who easily loses control of himself is very touchy.

In the next task, 3B students were given words they needed to match with the correct explanations, 0.75 points each. The task included the following words and explanations.

The words are: **honest, hard-working, polite, rude, dishonest, lazy**

The subsequent explanations are:

1. You can say this about a person who says "please" and "thank you".
2. You can say this about a person who always works much.
3. Someone who lies or steals.
4. Someone who never lies or steals.
5. Someone who doesn't like to work. 6. Someone who is not polite.

In task 3 C, students were given 4 faces and 4 adjectives. Their task was to match the faces with the adjectives that corresponded to the faces. For each correct answer, students could get 0.75 points. In Stage 3, the task for the EG was developed around the same vocabulary. Before the main stage, a questionnaire was given

to detect students' individual learning styles, which was created using MS Office forms.

Individual learning style questionnaire.

In round 1, students were then given slips of paper on which they wrote one noun and one adjective, after which all the slips were collected and put in a paper bag. Several students came and explained the trait on the paper without saying the word itself, using gestures, descriptions, and acting out the trait. The student who guessed correctly got a point. In round 2, students had to act out the trait, using no words. For the final 3rd round, a one-word clue could be used by the explaining student. For example, if the trait was "generous", the clue could be "kind." Students with 9 points or higher won the game. Even students in CG got so excited that they asked to play the game too, but without grading. After organizing the lessons, students were given a post-test in the form of an optional test with 10 questions (1 point each). The post-test included the words utilized in stages 2 and 3. Learners were asked to scan the QR code and do the task. This stage was done to collect the precise data for further analysis.

Post-test tasks

Research Findings Research findings show the statistical information for all stages. Taking a look at the results of the questionnaire, it becomes clear that the students mainly face difficulties when dealing with vocabulary. Overall, the bar chart highlights that most students encountered substantial difficulties in remembering, understanding, and using new vocabulary units. Many felt frustrated by the time and effort involved in learning new words. These findings emphasize the importance of developing creative and tailored methods for all students to effectively acquire and retain vocabulary skills.

Bar Chart 1. Results of the questionnaire

The analysis of the pre-test results for both the experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) reveals

varying levels of vocabulary proficiency. Table 2 depicts the grade range among the students in CG and EG. Table 2.

Pre-test results among CG and EG

Classification	Score	Pre-test for CG		EG	
		Student number	Percentage	Student Number	Percentage
Excellent	9-10	2	22.22%	1	11.11%
Very Good	7-8	1	11.11%	3	33.33%
Good	5-6	1	11.11%	0	0.00%
Average	3-4	2	22.22%	4	44.44%
Poor	1-2	3	33.33%	2	22.22%
Total		9	100.00%	9	100.00%

In the Experimental Group (EG), 1 out of 9 students scored "Excellent" (9–10), and 2 scored "Very Good" (7–8), showing a strong grasp of vocabulary. No students were in the "Good" range (5–6), while 4 were "Average" and 2 "Poor," indicating a performance gap. In the Control Group (CG), 2 students scored "Excellent," 1 "Very Good," and 1 "Good." Meanwhile, 2 students were "Average" and 3 "Poor," highlighting the

need for better support strategies. Overall, the results suggest that while a few students in both groups have a strong foundation, the majority require additional support to improve their vocabulary skills. The CG shows a slightly higher number of excellent performers, but also a larger proportion in the "Poor" category. Bar chart 2 more expressively depicts the results of the pre-test.

Bar Chart 2. Results of the Pre-test among CG and EG

The comparison of the post-test results between the Control Group (CG) and the Experimental Group (EG), on the other hand, reveals a stark contrast in vocabulary mastery, emphasizing the effectiveness of the VAK learning styles-based tasks. It illustrates how integrating visual, kinesthetic, and auditory techniques can significantly enhance language acquisition. Data collected from nine students revealed generally low scores in vocabulary, contextual usage, and emotion

identification tasks (collective score: 10 points). Only two participants achieved scores within the "Good" range (5.75-6). Four participants were assigned "Average" (3.5-4), marked by erratic execution as well as error-ridden emotion recognition. Three participants received "Poor" scores (1.25-2), demonstrating inadequate vocabulary and contextual awareness, confirming the necessity for specialized remedial intervention. The results of the CG are represented in table 3.

Table 3.

Results of the experiment with CG

Student	Task A(2.5 pts)	TaskB(4.5pts)	TaskC (3pts)	Total(10 pts)	Performance
1	2/2.5	1.5/4.5	0/3	3.5	Average
2	0.5/2.5	0.75/4.5	0/3	1.25	Poor
3	1/2.5	0/4.5	0.75/3	1.75	Poor
4	0.5/2.5	0.75/4.5	0.75/3	2	Poor
5	1.5/2.5	1.5/4.5	0.75/3	3.75	Average
6	1.5/2.5	2.25/4.5	2.25/3	6	Good
7	0.5/2.5	1.5/4.5	2/3	4	Average
8	1.5/2.5	2.25/4.5	2/3	5.75	Good
9	2/2.5	3/4.5	0.75/3	5.75	Good

Students demonstrated different levels of motivation according to their individual preferences. The performance of students characterized as Visual and Kinesthetic was outstanding: two achieved 9/10 (Excellent) using hands-on materials, one scored 8/10 (Very Good) with a blended approach. This group also excelled: one earned 7/10 for participation integrating speech and physical action alongside vocabulary gaps, while the

other scored 8/10 demonstrating stronger verbal engagement compared to inconsistent physical participation. Participants classified as Auditory and Visual achieved scores of 9/10 and 8/10, using both styles. All type learners (Visual, Kinesthetic, and Auditory) excelled scoring 9/10 and 8/10 for flexibility and multi-faceted task accomplishment. Table 4 illustrates the grades students got in EG.

Table 4.

Results of the experiment with EG

Student	Learning Styles	Grade	Improvement	Performance
1	Visual and Kinesthetic	8/10	Increased attention to task execution, using gestures and visual aids effectively.	Very Good
2	Visual and Kinesthetic	9/10	Excellent use of kinesthetic activities, demonstrating improved focus and engagement. Minor improvements needed in vocabulary recall.	Excellent
3	Visual and Kinesthetic	8/10	Well-balanced visual aids and physical involvement, increasing task completion efficiency.	Very Good
4	Auditory and Kinesthetic	7/10	Clearer verbal explanations, combined with physical demonstrations, enhanced learning, though, there is a need of more focus on vocabulary accuracy.	Very Good
5	Auditory and Kinesthetic	8/10	Improved auditory participation, but requires more consistent physical interaction with the task.	Very Good
6	Auditory and Visual	9/10	Well-executed auditory and visual elements, showing strong engagement but room for improvement in vocabulary retention.	Excellent

7	Auditory and Visual	8/10	Engaged with both auditory and visual components, making progress with task completion.	Very Good
8	Visual, Kinesthetic, and Auditory	9/10	Great use of a combination of all three styles, showing strong adaptability and improved task outcomes.	Excellent
9	Visual, Kinesthetic, and Auditory	8/10	Balanced use of all styles, with clear improvement in communication and task accuracy.	Very Good

In summary, the students who combined multiple learning styles (visual, auditory, and kinesthetic) tended to perform the best, with most scoring Very Good to Excellent for their ability to engage and adapt effectively throughout the task. The conducted post-test

results would determine the real difference of excellence between the groups, namely showing the effect of the VAK learning styles-based activities on students' vocabulary improvement. The results of the post-test between the CG and EG is shown in Table 5.

Table 5.

Results of the Post-test with CG and EG

Performance	Score	CG		EG	
		Student number	Percentage	Student number	Percentage
Excellent	9-10	0	0.00%	4	≈ 44.44%
Very Good	7-8	1	11.11%	5	≈ 55.55%
Good	5-6	3	≈ 33.33%	0	0.00%
Average	3-4	4	44.44%	0	0.00%
Poor	1-2	1	11.11%	0	0.00%
Total		9	100%	9	100%

Within the Control Group, no students achieved an "Excellent" score (9-10), while 4 students (≈44.44%) in the Experimental Group did. Only 1 student (11.11%) from the Control Group achieved the "Very Good" (7-8) level. This was significantly lower than the 5 students (≈55.55%) in the Experimental Group who obtained this level. Also, 3 students (≈33.33%) in the Control Group were classified as "Good" (5-6), while no students in the Experimental Group achieved this classification. Strikingly, 4 students (44.44%) from the Control Group were classified as "Average" (3-4), with

1 student (11.11%) classified as "Poor" (1-2). The Experimental Group did not include students with these lower categorizations. Overall, 100% of Experimental Group students scored 7 or higher compared to almost 55% of Control Group students scoring 6 or lower. These findings emphasize the impact of stimulating, multimodal teaching techniques on vocabulary retention and overall student performance. The contrast of the grades of the post-test is more vividly represented in diagram 1 below.

Diagram 1. Post-test grades among CG and EG

Conclusion

This research confirms the effectiveness of the VAK learning model in teaching vocabulary in ESL/EFL contexts. The VAK model takes into consideration different ways of learning and provides strategies which foster engagement with the language material on a deeper level. The experimental study carried out with high school students revealed that those exposed to VAK-based vocabulary instruction had greater improvements in both receptive and productive vocabulary skills than their peers taught through conventional approaches. Alongside the measurable academic benefits, the VAK approach stimulated a more active and student-centered classroom atmosphere. Learners were empowered by participating in activities, improving their vocabulary retention, and were additionally motivated and confident when using new phrases in context. Such outcomes reinforce the previously mentioned theoretical arguments that instruction which incorporates multiple senses stimulates learning on cognitive and emotional levels, resulting in more profound, sustained learning. The case study carried out in a secondary school has shown the significant relevance of the VAK learning model within the framework of the Armenian educational system. Its applicability is most notable considering the interplay and sequencing of the visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities within the system. Lastly, the VAK learning model serves as a strong foundation for vocabulary instruction, transforming the outcomes of instruction and learning. This emphasizes the need to change from model approaches to teaching and learning towards more comprehensive, student-centered methods. Such a shift enables teachers to create conditions for learners to develop not only linguistically and cognitively, but also personally.

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